

THE IMPORTANCE OF USING INTERNATIONAL ASSESSMENT PROGRAMS IN THE GENERAL EDUCATION SYSTEM

Roila Yuldoshvoyevna Xaydarova

Technology teacher at school

№14 of Bostonliq district, Tashkent region

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10403187>

Abstract. *This article presents the importance of using international assessment criteria in general secondary education institutions. The test of the international program for evaluating the educational achievements of students determines the knowledge of schoolchildren in the countries of the world and the ability to apply them in practice. It is detailed that the best practices aimed at improving the quality of education by evaluating and monitoring the development of the fields of education and science, as in foreign countries, should be involved in the field.*

Keywords: *assessment, monitoring, international assessment, PISA, PIRLS, TIMSS, TALIS.*

As a result of the reforms carried out in our country in recent years, huge economic growth indicators are being achieved, increasing the demand for qualified personnel and mature specialists in all fields. This in itself requires increasing the interest of our students in lessons and increasing the attention of teachers to all-round education and upbringing. The fact that the above requirements are very important for the education system means that, as in most foreign countries, it is necessary to attract the best practices aimed at improving the quality of education by evaluating and monitoring the development of education and science. Today, the analysis of the educational experience of developed countries shows that PISA (International Program for the Assessment of Student Achievement), PIRLS (Reading and Comprehension of the Text), which determines the quality, level and level of education there are a number of international programs, such as TIMSS (International Monitoring of the Quality of Mathematics and Science at School), which are widely used as a criterion for improving the quality of education in developed countries. The Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) is an assessment of the literacy level of 15-year-old students in reading, mathematics and natural sciences.

PISA is an international program for evaluating the achievements of students in the field of education, the test in which evaluates the knowledge of schoolchildren in the world and the ability to apply them in practice. The main goal of the program is to assess the ability of 15-year-old students to use the knowledge and experience they acquire at school in solving various life tasks in social relations and human activities. This test is held once every three years. Only 15-year-old teenagers participate in the test. The PISA program aimed at monitoring the quality of school education is conducted in three main areas: reading, mathematics and social science literacy.

In 2015 alone, more than 70 countries participated in the PISA international program test. In general, the PISA program has a significant impact on the education policy of countries. Based on the results of the research, each country objectively determines its strengths and weaknesses in

the field of education, sees its position in relation to other countries, and determines its directions and strategies for improving the educational process in educational institutions.

Progress in International Reading and Literacy Study (PIRLS) — to assess the level of reading and comprehension of primary 4 students PIRLS — readiness of primary school students in reading and receiving text and is to identify and evaluate the specific characteristics of the educational system that cause students to achieve different achievements. Of course, such research is of great importance for workers in the field of public education, scientists, methodologists, teachers, parents and public representatives.

Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) - assessment of the mastery level of 4th and 8th grade students in mathematics and natural sciences TIMSS - is also widely used in the education system of the world countries.

The TIMSS program is organized by the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievements (IEA), and this study examines the level of mathematics and social science education among 4th and 8th grade students. determines quality, level, attitude to science, interest.

The Teaching and Learning International Survey (TALIS) is conducted every 4 years to study the teaching and learning environment and the working conditions of teachers in general secondary educational institutions. Similar to the PIRLS study, this study will conduct additional surveys of students, school administrators, and teachers to identify key barriers to learning in science. This makes it possible to compare educational standards and educational efficiency developed in that country with other countries.

According to the results of the 2015 TIMSS research, the educational system of countries such as the USA, Singapore, Hong Kong, the Republic of Korea, Japan, Russia, and Great Britain have the highest indicators. It should be recognized that in these countries, in order to master high technologies, industrialization and achieve high level of development, special attention is paid to mastering specific sciences at a high level, in which students are more than innate talents and abilities. It is established that the number of students in a group or class does not exceed 16 people in the teaching of specific subjects. Such an experience is also available in the United States, and since 1999, taking into account that one teacher can educate 16 children during a 40-minute lesson, the number of students in groups in educational institutions has been increased by the president's decision. It is defined as 16 people.

PISA's reading literacy assessment tools have changed dramatically. In this regard, we saw that Russia's results also deteriorated slightly in 2018. Also, not only a new evaluation format (computer platform) was introduced to evaluate students' tests, but also completely different texts were offered to students: multidimensional texts, where it is necessary to identify conflicts, determine the point of view or the quality of sources texts. Therefore, there may not be a big shift in the results of Uzbek schoolchildren in this direction.

PISA tests are administered in 5 areas: Reading, Mathematical Literacy, Science, Collaborative Problem Solving and Financial Literacy.

In the tests, the main attention is paid to the fact that the students know the most basic concepts in these areas, acquire basic knowledge and skills, and are able to use them in real life situations! These tests are not intended to test the knowledge of students on specific topics during the lesson!

PISA tests use four different test methods:

One-answer tests;

Multiple answer tests;

Questions with short or detailed answers;

The student's opinion on the solution of a problem (usually such the examiner has common answers to the questions, the student's answer is not required to exactly match the test maker's answer, the student's creativity is supported).

In addition, at the same time as the tests, it is planned to receive questionnaires from the students. PISA: Main directions Reading literacy: A person's ability to understand and react to information given in the form of a text, to be able to use the information he has read in the process of active participation in the life of society, to increase his knowledge and capabilities. Here, the concept of reading literacy takes on a broad meaning. The goal of this course is for the student to understand the text, which includes a fragment of the given artistic work, biography, letter, document, articles from newspapers and magazines, various manuals, geographical maps, etc. it is to determine their competencies such as being able to think about the content, evaluate the content of the text and give their own opinion about what they have read.

Mathematical Literacy: It examines whether a person knows the place of mathematics in the world in which he lives, can correctly and fully justify mathematical processes. It is the main aim of this department to ensure that the individual can use mathematics in a way that meets the current and future needs of the creative, curious and thinking person for mathematical knowledge. The term literacy is used in this section to indicate that the purpose of this section is not to determine the extent to which students have mastered the knowledge normally provided in the school curriculum. The main focus is on being able to use mathematical knowledge in different life situations, using different methods of thinking and making intuitive decisions. But answering these types of questions may require knowledge and skills provided in the school curriculum. The tests in this area usually offer math-related situations that can be encountered in different areas of life (medicine, housing, sports, etc.).

Literacy of natural and scientific sciences: the competence to identify problems that can be solved scientifically in life events, draw conclusions based on observations and experiments. These conclusions are the main goal of this department to understand the world around us and to understand the changes occurring in it as a result of human activity, to make the necessary decisions accordingly.

As a conclusion, it can be said that through the international assessment program, the aim is to form the skills of the 21st century in our students and create a solid foundation for training competitive personnel. Because today, the need for the most knowledgeable personnel in any field that can withstand global competitiveness is felt in every aspect of today's social life.

REFERENCES

1. Ш.Х.Кулиева ТЕХНОЛОГИК ТАЪЛИМ ЎҚИТУВЧИЛАРИНИ ТАЙЁРЛАШДА ТЕХНОЛОГИК МАДАНИЯТНИНГ ЎРНИ Eurasian Journal of Social Sciences, Philosophy and Culture 2 (5), 16-20.
2. Ш.Х.Кулиева Аксиологический подход в профессионально- педагогической подготовке будущего учителя Казанский педагогический журнал, 48-52.

3. El papel de las tecnologías pedagógicas modernas en la formación de la competencia comunicativa de los estudiantes. KS Halimovna, MO Nurilloevna, K.D.Radzhabovna, RG Shavkatovna Religación. Revista de Ciencias Sociales Humanidades 4 (15), 261-266.